

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D5.1

**Prioritisation of identified
topics for advanced
technologies from Phase 1
actions (WP5)**

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ABSTRACT

Work package 5 (WP5) of the HARPERS project aims to (a) identify the obstacles and issues that could hamper the implementation of advanced technologies¹ in waste management and decommissioning, (b) identify opportunities for more aligned practices, methodologies and approaches across Member States (MS), and (c) investigate and conclude on the need and benefits of the adoption of and more aligned approach to advanced technologies, to enhance waste management and decommissioning operations in Europe.

Task 5.1 of the HARPERS project is focused on the prioritisation of needs and opportunities in advanced technologies (Phase 1a) to support increased acceptance and use of cutting-edge technologies and tools.

This document describes the process used to prioritise the topics identified for WP5 and presents the outcome of this process. The top priority thematic topics have been selected through expert discussions, analysis of information and engagement with stakeholders. For WP5, a semi-quantitative prioritisation process was adopted, based on the use of weighting factors for the different types of challenge associated with the topics and the drivers for implementation, together with an analysis of the topics by the work package partners. This provided a quantitative ranking of topics which was then followed by a qualitative down-selection of the topics by reviewing (i) their importance vs urgency and (ii) their impact vs effort. Three priority topics in the areas of Waste Treatment, Automation and Robotics, and Digitalisation were identified for future detailed analysis in Phase 2 of the HARPERS project.

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¹ Advanced technologies include novel and advanced waste treatment technologies and waste-forms, robotic and automated systems, digital technologies and advanced modelling approaches and tools.

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1. Introduction

Work package (WP) 5 of the HARPERS project aims to:

- identify the obstacles and issues that could hamper the implementation of advanced technologies in waste management and decommissioning,
- identify opportunities for more aligned practices, methodologies and approaches across Member States (MS), and
- investigate and conclude on the need and benefits of the adoption of and more aligned approach to advanced technologies, to enhance waste management and decommissioning operations in Europe.

Task 5.1 of the HARPERS Project WP5 is focused on the prioritisation of needs and opportunities in advanced technologies (Phase 1a) to support increased acceptance and use of cutting-edge technologies and tools. Top priority thematic topics for future detailed analysis in Phase 2 of the HARPERS project have been selected through expert discussions, analysis of information and engagement with stakeholders.

The overall approach to identifying and prioritising the topics is described in [1], [2] (<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>) and is summarised as:

1. Perform a gap analysis to identify recommendations/needs/opportunities relevant to the work packages and HARPERS project scope [1]
2. Identify a list of thematic questions/topics (grouped into categories) based on (a) the findings of the gap analysis, (b) an initial list of “needs and opportunities” formed during development of the project, (c) discussion with HARPERS project partners [1], [3]
3. Define selection criteria to support prioritisation of topics, based on drivers for implementation in decommissioning and waste management [4]

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4. Hold stakeholder engagement sessions (including external stakeholders and HARPERS project partners (internal stakeholders)) to discuss drivers, topics and areas of importance [1], [2]
5. Analysis of stakeholder feedback [2]
6. Prioritisation of topics for Phase 2 by work package partners, taking account of the stakeholder feedback (this report)
7. Discussion of the list of priority topics with the stakeholder community (consolidated results) [2]

Milestone MS5.1 [3] presents the list of thematic topics (challenges and needs) for WP5 (Advanced Technologies), which are grouped into three categories: (1) Waste Treatment, (2) Automation and Robotics, and (3) Digitalisation. Milestone MS5.2 [4] lists the selection criteria for prioritisation in Phase 1, which are based on drivers for implementation relating to societal, actor-specific, scientific and financial impacts. Appendix 1 provides the list of topics taken forward for discussion with stakeholders and subsequent prioritisation for Phase 2, while Appendix 2 presents the list of selection criteria (drivers for implementation).

Two stakeholder engagement sessions were held for WP5 on 18th January 2023 and 2nd February 2023. The sessions involved a combination of online polls and open discussion to gain feedback from participants (both internal and external stakeholders) on the key drivers for the adoption of advanced technologies, the most important topics for further analysis, and the main challenges and barriers associated with the topics. Details of the stakeholder engagement sessions and the results from the online polls are provided in [1], [2] and Appendix 3.

The proposed approach to prioritisation under Step 6 above, was presented and discussed at the HARPERS Consortium Meeting in April 2023 and is outlined in [2]. The approach is semi-quantitative, based on the use of Weighting Factors (WF) for the different (a) topic categories, (b) types of challenge, and (c) drivers for implementation, together with an analysis of the topics by the work package partners against the types

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of challenge and the drivers. This quantitative ranking of topics is then followed by a further qualitative down-selection of the topics by reviewing (i) their importance vs urgency and (ii) their impact vs effort.

The approach to prioritisation for WP5 was slightly modified to the approach described above in that there was no assignment of WFs to the different topic categories. This is because there are only three topic categories for WP5 and it was considered appropriate to select one topic from each of these categories to take forward into Phase 2. This would allow analysis in Phase 2 across the breadth of areas covered under Advanced Technologies.

This report focuses on describing and presenting the results from Step 6 of the approach to identifying and prioritising topics (see above). The following sections describe the derivation of the WFs, the analysis and scoring of the topics based on the types of challenges and the drivers, and the qualitative down-selection of topics.

2. Prioritisation of WP5 topics for Phase 2

Weighting factors (WFs)

WFs for the 'Type of Challenge' and for 'Drivers' were assigned based on the combined results from the two WP5 stakeholder sessions (Appendix 3).

Weighting factors for 'Type of Challenge'

Six types of challenge (or barrier) were defined (see Table 1) for the purpose of identifying the challenges associated with the different topics. These were developed by the WP5 team as part of the preparation for the stakeholder sessions and subsequent analysis. The challenges relate to key aspects of technical, safety, economic and social. In the stakeholder sessions, the participants were asked, for each of the three WP5 categories, to select the top two challenge types associated with the category.

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Type of challenge or barrier	Description for WP5 Advanced Technologies
Technological and operational (availability and accessibility)	Challenges and barriers associated with the availability and accessibility of technologies, e.g. components and interfaces, as well as demonstration of the technologies under relevant scenarios, e.g. experience, case studies.
Regulatory (licensing, safety, security, environmental safety, regulatory confidence)	Challenges and barriers associated with demonstrating nuclear safety, security, environmental safety, etc. of the technologies to meet regulatory requirements. Perceived challenges in gaining regulatory approvals for the use of advanced technologies. Potential limitations in guidance to address regulatory requirements.
Safety and Environment (safety case, dose)	Challenges and barriers associated with developing the safety and environmental safety cases for use of advanced technologies (may be subsumed into 'Regulatory'). Challenges regarding demonstrating that doses to workers and the public are safe.
Economic (cost/benefit)	Challenges and barriers associated with efficiency and flexibility of the technologies, demonstrating that the technologies are cost-effective and that the cost of implementing advanced technologies is justified on the basis of the benefits gained.
Societal (public trust/confidence, stakeholder issues)	Perceived challenges in gaining public trust and confidence in the use of advanced technologies, as well as addressing other stakeholder issues, e.g. worker concerns
Competence and Skills (experience)	Challenges and barriers associated with availability of the necessary competence, skills and experience required for the adoption of advanced technologies, e.g. in the developers, supply chain, workers, regulators.

Table 1 – Types of challenge and associated description for WP5

The stakeholder results from the online polls were used to derive WFs (normalised so that the highest weighting factor was 1) for each type of challenge, specific to each

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category of topics. The stakeholder results and corresponding WFs are presented in Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4.

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Type of challenge: Waste Treatment	Stakeholder Results (%)	Normalised WF
Technological and operational (availability and accessibility)	23	0.32
Regulatory (licensing, safety, security, regulatory confidence)	70	1.00
Safety and Environment (safety case, dose)	35	0.50
Economic (cost/benefit)	40	0.57
Societal (public trust/confidence, stakeholder issues)	28	0.39
Competence and Skills (experience)	10	0.14

Table 2 – Normalised weighting factors for ‘type of challenge’ for Waste Treatment category

Type of challenge: Automation and Robotics	Stakeholder Results (%)	Normalised WF
Technological and operational (availability and accessibility)	51	0.95
Regulatory (licensing, safety, security, regulatory confidence)	54	1.00
Safety and Environment (safety case, dose)	21	0.38
Economic (cost/benefit)	41	0.76
Societal (public trust/confidence, stakeholder issues)	18	0.33
Competence and Skills (experience)	21	0.38

Table 3 – Normalised weighting factors for ‘type of challenge’ for Automation and Robotics category

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Type of challenge: Digitalisation	Stakeholder Results (%)	Normalised WF
Technological and operational (availability and accessibility)	57	0.88
Regulatory (licensing, safety, security, regulatory confidence)	65	1.00
Safety and Environment (safety case, dose)	11	0.17
Economic (cost/benefit)	22	0.33
Societal (public trust/confidence, stakeholder issues)	24	0.38
Competence and Skills (experience)	27	0.42

Table 4 – Normalised weighting factors for ‘type of challenge’ for Digitalisation category

Weighting factors for ‘Drivers’

In the stakeholder sessions, the participants were asked ‘What are the main drivers for adopting advanced technologies?’ and to select the top three drivers from the list presented in Appendix 2. The results are presented in Table 5, along with the normalised WFs and the top 5 drivers.

Drivers (for implementation)	Stakeholder results (%)	Normalised WF	Top 5 drivers
Economic renewal and growth	23	0.36	
Protection of citizens / environment	64	1	1
Public trust and confidence	36	0.56	3
Processes, products and services	31	0.48	4
Capacity to improve performance	56	0.88	2

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Contribution to competences and skills development	13	0.2	
Improvement of national/international networks	5	0.08	
Quality in science and technology development	26	0.4	5
Innovation capacity	18	0.28	
Revenue and turnover	18	0.28	
Sufficient investment	3	0.04	

Table 5 – Normalised weighting factors for drivers for adopting advanced technologies

Scoring of topics

The topics were then analysed by the WP5 partners based on the types of challenge and the drivers. This was undertaken in two stages: (a) deriving a total weight based on challenges, for each topic, and (b) calculating a score for each topic based on the associated challenges and the impact of the topic on the top 5 drivers for advanced technologies (Table 5). These stages are described in the following sections.

Total weight based on challenges associated with each topic

Two main challenges were assigned to each topic based on the discussions at the stakeholder sessions as well as the experience and knowledge of the WP5 partners.

The total weight for each topic based on challenges (Challenge WF) was calculated by taking the mean value of the WFs for the two main challenges identified per topic. The results are presented in Figure 1.

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Score for each topic based on challenges and drivers

For each category, the topics were then analysed in terms of their impact on the top 5 drivers relevant to advanced technologies, by assigning a value for the 'level of impact', on the driver of High (1), Medium (0.5) or Low (0.1)².

An overall score for each topic was then calculated by:

1. Multiplying each Driver WF, D_{WF} , by the 'level of impact' value, I , for that driver
2. Adding together the values from step 1 (5 values for the top 5 drivers)
3. Multiplying the value from step 2 by the Challenge WF, C_{WF}

i.e. Topic score = $(D_{WF1} \cdot I_1 + D_{WF2} \cdot I_2 + D_{WF3} \cdot I_3 + D_{WF4} \cdot I_4 + D_{WF5} \cdot I_5) C_{WF}$

The results of this process are shown in Figure 2. For each category, the scores are colour-coded according to their percentile over the range of scores for the category: 'green' (Score $\geq 75\%$), 'orange' ($50\% \leq$ Score $< 75\%$), 'red' ($25\% \leq$ Score $< 50\%$), 'grey' (Score $< 25\%$). (Note that in Figure 2 there are no topics that were scored as 'red'.)

² Initial assignments were made by the WP5 lead team based on their experience and judgement. The assignments were then reviewed by the WP5 partners.

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Category	Topic no.	Topic description	Challenge/need	Type of challenge	Type of challenge	WF CHALLENGE
Waste Treatment	1	New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration	Need for standard approaches to technology assessment and qualification Need for compatibility of technologies with waste form qualification Need for guidance and sharing of experience on new decontamination products/tools and remediation technologies, particularly deployment and secondary waste aspects Need for transfer of knowledge from more advanced to less advanced programmes	Technological and operational	Regulatory	0.66
	2	Adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques including additive manufacturing	Need for transfer of knowledge and technologies from other industries and sharing of experience Need for qualification of process and product	Technological and operational	Regulatory	0.66
	3	New waste treatment and immobilisation technologies	Need for standard approaches to technology assessment and qualification Need for compatibility of technologies with waste form qualification Need for guidance and sharing of experience on new waste treatment and immobilisation technologies Need for transfer of knowledge from more advanced to less advanced programmes	Technological and operational	Regulatory	0.66
	4	Harmonised waste-form assessment protocols	Need for harmonised waste-form assessment protocols Need for standard approaches to assessing secondary wastes and compatibility with waste packages Need for standard approaches to demonstrating compliance	Safety and Environment	Regulatory	0.75
	5	Remote in-situ characterisation / non contact or non-destructive evaluation	Need for sharing of experience, particularly on ability to deploy on plant Need for increased alignment of technologies to the challenges - communication between challenge owners and developers	Technological and operational	Competence and Skills	0.23
	6	Standards for mobile treatment systems	Need for greater standardisation to support increased flexibility for use across facilities, different users and countries	Technological and operational	Economic	0.45

Automation and Robotics	1	Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality.	Demonstration of security and safety to regulators Need for close communication with regulators during technology development Demonstrating applicability in a range of environments from basic to harsh Need for guidance on safety case demonstration appropriate to the environment Standardisation of architecture for robotics and standards for manufacturing to support verification and validation stages Need for standardisation of protocols, control systems and interfaces Need for sharing experience where robotics has been evaluated and used on sites for different applications	Regulatory	Technological and operational	0.98
	2	Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging.	Need for guidance on safety case demonstration (technology is at demonstration stage) - requires regulatory engagement.	Safety and Environment	Regulatory	0.69
	3	Automation of waste stores, learning from advanced digital logistics practice.	Need for guidance on safety case demonstration (technology is at concept design stage) - requires regulatory engagement. Need for transfer of knowledge and technologies from other industries and sharing of experience	Safety and Environment	Regulatory	0.69
	4	Smart decontamination techniques - targeting contamination through sensing, local decontamination and removal of the hazard from the system.	Technology development still required Need for close communication with regulators during technology development Need for guidance from regulators on how to approach safety demonstration	Regulatory	Technological and operational	0.98

Digitalisation	1	'Standardised' DTW and advanced BIM technology and their application.	Need for standardised digital technologies and best practice guidance Need for guidelines/standards on the implementation of digital technologies, the data used and generated and the data quality (how to qualify this) - data protocols Need to build competency of users to assess and use the data from digital technologies - skills and interfaces Need to evaluate the regulatory implications of using advanced digital technologies Need for sharing of experience where technologies are already deployed in nuclear sector	Technological and operational	Regulatory	0.94
	2	Standardisation of protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation	Security of data used with digital technologies, including storage, access and transfer; cyber security Need to understand what needs to be/what can be standardised involving cross-industry engagement and regulators	Regulatory	Technological and operational	0.94
	3	Standardisation of digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI)	Need for digital technologies to be accessible to users (e.g. plant owners/operators) without requiring knowledge of the underpinning coding/technology Need to agree on what needs to be/what can be standardised in terms of architecture and frameworks involving cross-industry engagement	Technological and operational	Regulatory	0.94
	4	Automation of site mapping – coupling the use of sensors, Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and deployment methods (UAV, land based automated vehicles etc).	Need for sharing of experience on application of automated site mapping Security of data - cyber security	Technological and operational	Regulatory	0.94
	5	Standardisation of 3D modelling protocols	Lack of standardisation in the nuclear industry for use of 3D modelling and simulation, typically constrained by the offerings of a specific technology platform provider Need for interoperability of digital technologies for modelling and simulation	Technological and operational	Competence and Skills	0.65

Note: Discussions with stakeholders indicated that the 'Regulatory' type of challenge related mainly to cyber security (for digital technologies) and challenges in demonstrating safety (safety case) to meet regulatory requirements.

Figure 1 – Total weighting factor for 'type of challenge' (Challenge WF)

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Scoring of WP5 topics based on challenges and drivers

Impact on driver	
High	1
Medium	0.5
Low	0.1

Category	Topic no.	Topic description	CHALLENGE WF	DRIVERS					SCORE
				Protection of citizens / environment	Capacity to improve performance	Public trust and confidence	Processes, products and services	Quality in science and technology development	
				1.00	0.88	0.56	0.48	0.40	
Waste Treatment	1	New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration	0.66	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	1.9
	2	Adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques including additive manufacturing	0.66	0.1	1	0.1	0.5	0.5	1.0
	3	New waste treatment and immobilisation technologies	0.66	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	1.9
	4	Harmonised waste-form assessment protocols	0.75	0.1	1	0.5	0.5	0.1	1.2
	5	Remote in-situ characterisation / non contact or non-destructive evaluation	0.23	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	0.7
	6	Standards for mobile treatment systems	0.45	0.1	0.5	0.5	1	0.1	0.6

Category	Topic no.	Topic description	CHALLENGE WF	DRIVERS					SCORE
				Protection of citizens / environment	Capacity to improve performance	Public trust and confidence	Processes, products and services	Quality in science and technology development	
				1.00	0.88	0.56	0.48	0.40	
Automation and Robotics	1	Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality.	0.98	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.1	2.4
	2	Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging.	0.69	1	1	1	0.5	0.1	1.9
	3	Automation of waste stores, learning from advanced digital logistics practice.	0.69	1	1	1	0.5	0.1	1.9
	4	Smart decontamination techniques - targeting contamination through sensing, local decontamination and removal of the hazard from the system.	0.98	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.1	2.4

Category	Topic no.	Topic description	CHALLENGE WF	DRIVERS					SCORE
				Protection of citizens / environment	Capacity to improve performance	Public trust and confidence	Processes, products and services	Quality in science and technology development	
				1.00	0.88	0.56	0.48	0.40	
Digitalisation	1	'Standardised' DTW and advanced BIM technology and their application.	0.94	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	2.2
	2	Standardisation of protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation	0.94	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	2.4
	3	Standardisation of digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI)	0.94	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	2.2
	4	Automation of site mapping – coupling the use of sensors, Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and deployment methods (UAV, land based automated vehicles etc).	0.94	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.1	2.3
	5	Standardisation of 3D modelling protocols	0.65	0.5	1	0.5	0.5	0.1	1.3

Figure 2 – Scoring of WP5 topics

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Final selection of priority topics

A qualitative evaluation of the top priority topics from the scoring stage, in terms of Importance/Urgency and Impact/Effort, was then carried out by the WP5 partners for each category, using the matrices in Figure 3. This provided a final selection of three topics (one from each category) for detailed evaluation in Phase 2 of the HARPERS project. Account was also taken of the stakeholder session results on the important topics in each category, which were found to be broadly consistent with the results of the quantitative scoring approach.

Figure 3 – Matrices for qualitative evaluation of the WP5 topics

An example of the qualitative analysis using the matrices is shown in Figure 4 for the Waste Treatment category. Topics 1 and 3 in this category were judged to be of high importance and high urgency and so were taken forward to be evaluated in terms of impact and effort. Addressing Topics 1 and 3 was considered to be able to provide a high impact with moderate effort. Furthermore, since these two topics had the same challenges and needs (e.g. more aligned approaches to technology assessment and qualification) associated with implementing new technologies, these topics were combined into a single priority topic regarding demonstration and implementation of new technologies for decontamination of buildings, waste treatment, waste immobilisation and environmental restoration.

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Figure 4 – Evaluation matrices for the Waste Treatment category

A similar approach was taken for the Automation and Robotics and the Digitalisation categories. For the Automation and Robotics category, Topics 1 and 4 had the highest score, however, Topic 1 was judged to be of high importance and urgency while Topic 4 was considered to be of lower (medium) importance and urgency. Nevertheless, it was thought that the challenges associated with Topic 4 (Smart decontamination techniques) would be partly considered through Topic 1 (Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management) and also within the Waste Treatment category Topic 1 (New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration).

In addition, Topics 2 and 3 in the Automation and Robotics category were reviewed by the WP5 partners and considered to form a subset of Topic 1, noting that Topic 2 had been considered by the stakeholders to be the second priority topic after Topic 1. Therefore, it was concluded that Topic 1 (Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management) was the priority topic for the Automation and Robotics category, but that the topic should reference elements of Topic 2 (Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging) and Topic 3

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(Automation of waste stores). This priority topic (Topic 1 combined with elements of Topics 2 and 3) was judged to have a high impact with moderate effort.

For the Digitalisation category, Topic 1 (Standardised digital twin (DT) and advanced Building Information Management (BIM) technology and their application) was considered to be of high importance and high urgency and would provide a high impact through a moderate level of effort. Topics 2, 3 and 5 were considered to form elements of Topic 1, while Topic 4 was judged to be of lower importance and urgency than Topic 1. Therefore, the priority topic for the Digitalisation category was identified as Topic 1 (Standardised DT and advanced BIM technology and their application), incorporating elements of Topic 2 (Standardisation of protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation), Topic 3 (Standardisation of digital architecture and frameworks – common human machine interface) and Topic 5 (Standardisation of 3D modelling protocols).

3. Summary of priority topics

The priority topics for WP5 for taking forward into Phase 2 of the HARPERS project are summarised in Table 6.

The prioritisation process and the resulting top 3 priority topics for WP5 were presented at a stakeholder session held on 30th May 2023.

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Topic no.	Description of topic	Main challenges	Main needs ³
1	New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration including waste treatment and immobilisation	Technological and operational Regulatory ⁴	Standard approaches to technology assessment and qualification Compatibility of technologies with waste form qualification Guidance and sharing of experience on new decontamination products/tools and remediation technologies, particularly deployment and secondary waste aspects Transfer of knowledge from more advanced to less advanced programmes
2	Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality. To include automation of waste sorting, application of smart decontamination	Regulatory ⁴ Technological and operational	Demonstration of security and safety to regulators Close communication with regulators during technology development Demonstrating applicability in a range of environments from basic to harsh Guidance on safety case demonstration appropriate to the environment Standardisation of architecture for robotics and standards for manufacturing to support verification and validation stages Standardisation of protocols, control systems and interfaces Transfer of knowledge and technologies from other industries and sharing of experience Sharing experience where robotics has been evaluated and used on sites for different applications

³ These needs were identified based on the feedback received from stakeholders as well as from the gap analysis.

⁴ Discussions with stakeholders indicated that the 'Regulatory' challenges were related mainly to challenges in demonstrating safety (safety case) to meet regulatory requirements.

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	techniques, segregation, sentencing, packaging and waste stores.		
3	'Standardised' digital twin and advanced Building Information Management (BIM) technology and their application, to include protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation, digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI) which will also benefit modelling protocols (3D).	Technological and operational Regulatory ⁵	<p>Standardised digital technologies and best practice guidance</p> <p>Guidelines/standards on the implementation of digital technologies, the data used and generated and the data quality (how to qualify this) - data protocols</p> <p>Build competency of users to assess and use the data from digital technologies - skills and interfaces</p> <p>Evaluate the regulatory implications of using advanced digital technologies</p> <p>Sharing of experience where technologies are already deployed in nuclear sector</p> <p>Security of data used with digital technologies, including storage, access and transfer; cyber security</p> <p>Understand what needs to be/what can be standardised involving cross-industry engagement and regulators</p> <p>Digital technologies to be accessible to users (e.g. plant owners/operators) without requiring knowledge of the underpinning coding/technology</p> <p>Standardisation in the nuclear industry for use of 3D modelling and simulation, typically constrained by the offerings of a specific technology platform provider</p> <p>Interoperability of digital technologies for modelling and simulation</p>

Table 6 – List of priority topics for WP5

⁵ Discussions with stakeholders indicated that the 'Regulatory' challenges were related mainly to cyber security and challenges in demonstrating safety (safety case) to meet regulatory requirements.

Prioritisation of identified topics for advanced technologies from Phase 1 actions
(WP5)

4. References

1. Maes, N., 2023. Deliverable D2.1: Work methodologies: Methods for identification and prioritisation of topics. Version 1.0. HARPERS project. EC Grant agreement no: 101060028.
2. Maes, N. et al., 2023. Deliverable D2.2: Analysis of stakeholder engagement results and definition of priority areas. Version 1.0. HARPERS project. EC Grant agreement no: 101060028.
3. Fowler, L., 2022. Milestone M5.1: List of thematic questions to Phase 1 (WP5 – Advanced Technologies). Version 1. HARPERS project. EC Grant agreement no: 101060028.
4. Fowler, L., 2022. Milestone MS3.2, MS4.2, MS5.2: List of selection criteria for prioritisation of topics in Phase 1 (WPs 3, 4 and 5). Version 1. HARPERS project. EC Grant agreement no: 101060028.
5. PREDIS, 2023. Milestone 2.4: PREDIS Strategic Research Agenda. Version 2, May 2023. EC Grant agreement no: 945098.
6. SHARE, 2021. D1.3: Definition of implementation qualifiers and instruments for implementation. Version 4, March 2021. EC Grant agreement no: 847626.

Prioritisation of identified topics for advanced technologies from Phase 1 actions
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Appendix 1: List of Topics for Work Package 5

Table 7 presents the list of topics for WP5 taken forward to the stakeholder sessions and the prioritisation process.

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	Topic (What?)	Why?
Waste treatment		
1	New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration	To optimise and reduce the volume and categories of waste generated by concrete structures to be decontaminated and soils to be excavated
2	Adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques including additive manufacturing	The use of rapid prototype / manufacturing techniques to allow for the early adoption of innovative solutions in the production of waste-forms
3	New waste treatment and immobilisation technologies	To reduce waste volumes and enhance waste-form performance. To handle difficult to treat wastes
4	Harmonised waste-form assessment protocols	To streamline innovation in and adoption of new waste processing technologies.
5	Remote in-situ characterisation / non-contact or non-destructive evaluation	To understand the nature of plant and waste. To reduce uncertainty in inventory, informing waste management & decommissioning strategies, decisions and appropriate automated material sentencing, including clearance of materials.
6	Standards for mobile treatment systems	To allow cross-facility and cross-border use of treatment technologies. Supporting small inventory users. Enable cost-effective and flexible systems.
Automation and Robotics		
7	Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused	Removing workers from hazardous exposure. Automation to reduce cost and schedule.

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	Topic (What?)	Why?
	technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality.	
8	Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging.	To enhance safety and deliver efficiency gains through automation. Reduced worker exposure - ALARP.
9	Automation of waste stores, learning from advanced digital logistics practice.	To enhance efficient waste and inventory management and safeguarding.
10	Smart decontamination techniques - targeting contamination through sensing, local decontamination and removal of the hazard from the system.	To remove the hazard from the plant, allowing safe, but more flexible, faster, cheaper approaches to dismantling
Digitalisation		
11	'Standardised' digital twin (DT) and advanced Building Information Management (BIM) technology and their application	To facilitate lifetime plant and waste operations, knowledge management and data retention, and to predict the performance of systems, nuclear plant, processes and packages. Support optimised decommissioning and waste management activities and to provide relevant up-to-date data.
12	Standardisation of protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation	To enable use of new IT solutions, and data transfer between smart devices

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	Topic (What?)	Why?
13	Standardisation of digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI)	To allow for the cross connectivity of digital and automation tools – ‘plug and play’ and to allow transfer between software packages. Standard HMI also aids mobility of staff between activities.
14	Automation of site mapping – coupling the use of sensors, Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and deployment methods (UAV, land based automated vehicles etc).	Provides data for management and regulatory oversight. To facilitate efficient site mapping for radiological contamination, interpretation through modelling including Enhanced Natural Attenuation models.
15	Standardisation of 3D modelling protocols	To allow easy transition between platforms (platform independent). Digital transformation provides an opportunity for improving safety and reducing costs.

Table 7 – List of topics

Note: This topic list is slightly modified to that in [3]. It was decided by WP5 that Topic 7 (‘Standardised’ digital twin and BIM technology, to predict the performance of systems, plant, processes and packages) [3] should be combined with Topic 12 (Application of advanced building information management systems to nuclear plants) [3]. The resulting topic is Topic 11 in Table 7.

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Appendix 2: Drivers for use in the prioritisation of topics

It was agreed by WP3, 4 and 5 that topics would be prioritised based on evaluation of a common set of selection criteria corresponding to drivers for implementation (Table 8). These relate to societal, actor-specific, scientific and financial impacts. These drivers have been used in the development of the Strategic Research Agenda⁶ for the PREDIS project [5] and were based on work undertaken in the SHARE project [6]. Each work package has determined which drivers are the most relevant to their scope as part of the stakeholder workshops.

Driver	Description
<p>Societal: Societal impacts address higher level area economics, perspectives of people, environmental protection and the overall trust and well-being of the society. These can be viewed at a local, municipality, regional, country or EU level.</p>	
<p>Economic renewal and growth</p>	<p>Leads to a sustainable increase in the number of work force/jobs and services needed, allowing existing companies to expand their offering or for new companies to enter the market. Provides economic benefits to a region, which can impact the quality and availability of societal public services in the area.</p> <p>Also linked to financial impacts.</p>
<p>Protection of citizens and environment</p>	<p>Leads to improved protection of citizens and the environment by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting the reduction of radioactive waste volumes, including between classes of waste (e.g., reduction in HLW to lower levels of waste)

⁶ The final version of the PREDIS Strategic Research Agenda will be published in May 2024 and subsequent dissemination activities implemented.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving waste classification • Supporting the conservation of the environment • Reducing hazards • Applying the waste hierarchy to prevent, minimise, re-use and recycle wastes • Reducing secondary waste production • Enables safer treatment, packing and storage of wastes, reducing the risk of human exposure (worker and public) and environmental accidents
Public trust and confidence	Engenders public trust and confidence through good planning, implementation and communication of programmes; good communication and transparency of decision making by regulators and governments; and timely and efficient policy formulation and implementation.
<p>Actor-specific: Actor-specific impacts reflect individual company or industry advances relating to processes, products and services, efficiency, competences</p>	
Processes, products and services	Supports the development of new / improved and innovative processes, products and services to address decommissioning and waste management, which in turn leads to the creation and expansion of companies. Provides solutions that create a competitive advantage, such as cost reduction or resource efficiency. Provides new products and innovations developed to higher Technology Readiness Levels (TRL 7, 8 and 9).
Capacity to improve performance	Provides improved performance by increasing the efficiency of tasks (e.g., by reducing the required labour and minimising the generation of secondary waste) and by reducing lead times for decommissioning and waste management by reducing the time needed for each task. Supports the reduction in regulatory review

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	times by integrating this with the planning phases and using standardised processes.
Contribution to competences and skills development	Supports the development and maintenance of a skilled and competent workforce for the duration of decommissioning and waste management programmes. Provides training, education and certification of the workforce, and services/tools for knowledge management, helping to increase efficiency and manage risks effectively, thus reducing accidents.
Improvement of national/international networks	Provides benefits to research and business communities through participation in research networks and business networks. Supports mobility between companies and combining expertise from multiple disciplines.
Scientific: Scientific impacts relate to technology development and innovation to drive improvements.	
Quality in science and technology development	Builds competences and skills in state-of-the-art technologies, practices and developments, through research collaboration and publication of work to assess research quality. Advances technology through TRL.
Innovation capacity	Develops innovation capacity to both introduce new products, services and processes to the market, and to develop in-house solutions.
Financial: Financial impacts relate to business solutions (linked to company growth and performance) and funding schemes.	
Revenue and turnover	Increases revenue and turnover of a company, leading to increased company growth and improved performance through demonstrating high quality services, tools and success in delivery.

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	Dependent on market potential and funding schemes, as well as ability to reduce liabilities.
Sufficient investment	Promotes adequate funding for decommissioning and waste management, and investment in the required supporting infrastructure and facilities.

Table 8 – List of selection criteria

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Appendix 3: Summary of the combined outputs from the HARPERS WP5 Advanced Technologies stakeholder session questions

Stakeholder Session 1: 18th January 2023 (32 participants)

Stakeholder Session 2: 2nd February 2023 (13 participants)

What do you see as the major opportunities for advanced technologies in decommissioning and waste management in the next 10/15 years? - Short answer (1 to 3 words)

33 participants responded to this question

Increased **efficiency** was highlighted as the main opportunity/benefit for adopting advanced technologies leading to reduced costs (**cost efficiency, cost reduction**).

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Use of technologies, such as **robotics** and **virtual reality**, can support increased **safety and security** and provide greater **protection of people**. Adoption of advanced technologies was also seen as a benefit for **public engagement**.

What are the main drivers for adopting advanced technologies? Select top 3 drivers

39 participants responded to this question

[Results indicate the percentage of participants that voted for the option.]

The main drivers for adopting advanced technologies, as voted by participants, were 'Protection of citizens / environment' and the 'Capacity to improve performance'.

Waste treatment

What do you consider are the most important topics under 'Waste treatment' to be further analysed within the HARPERS project? Select top 3 from the list

36 participants responded to this question

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[Results indicate the percentage of participants that voted for the option.]

What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics (Waste treatment)? Select top 2 from list

40 participants responded to this question

[Results indicate the percentage of participants that voted for the option.]

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Automation and Robotics

What do you consider are the most important topics under 'Automation and Robotics' to be further analysed within the HARPERS project? Select top 3 from the list

37 participants responded to this question

[Results indicate the percentage of participants that voted for the option.]

What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics (Automation and Robotics)? Select top 2 from list

39 participants responded to this question

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[Results indicate the percentage of participants that voted for the option.]

Digitalisation

What do you consider are the most important topics under 'Digitalisation' to be further analysed within the HARPERS project? Select top 3 from the list

35 participants responded to this question

[Results indicate the percentage of participants that voted for the option.]

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What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics (Digitalisation)? Select top 2 from list

37 participants responded to this question

[Results indicate the percentage of participants that voted for the option.]

Summary

The most important topics (top 3 in each category) based on the views of the workshop participants are listed below.

Waste treatment

- i. New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration
- ii. New waste treatment and immobilisation technologies
- iii. Remote in-situ characterisation / non contact or non-destructive evaluation

The main challenges / barriers were considered to be Regulatory challenges (includes safety case development).

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Automation and Robotics

- i. Adoption of robotics in decommissioning and waste management
- ii. Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging
- iii. Smart decontamination techniques

The main challenges / barriers were indicated to be Regulatory challenges (includes safety case development) and Technological and operational challenges.

Digitalisation

- i. Standardised DT and BIM technology and their application
- ii. Standardisation of protocols for security of data and data transfer
- iii. Automation of site mapping – coupling the use of sensors, GIS and deployment methods

The main challenges / barriers were indicated to be Regulatory challenges (includes cyber security and safety case development) and Technological and operational challenges.